

SOLUTIONS TO THE PROBLEM OF OZONE LAYER DEPLETION

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Abstract: The problems of environmental pollution are especially relevant today for all mankind in the modern world. One of these serious issues is the depletion of the ozone layer, the solution of which is possible only with the unification of the states of the entire world community. In order to implement the global policy aimed at protecting the ozone layer, each member state undertakes to create a national policy.

Keywords: ozone layer, chemicals, nature, law, international cooperation.

The ozone layer is part of the stratosphere at an altitude of 12 to 50 km. Ozone is a layer of increased concentration of O₂, about 3 mm thick. As a result of many external influences, the ozone layer begins to thin out compared to its natural state, and under certain conditions disappear completely over certain territories - ozone holes appear, fraught with irreversible consequences. At first they were observed closer to the south pole of

the Earth, but have recently been seen over the Asian part of Russia.¹⁰⁰

There are many possible causes of ozone depletion shield:

Firstly, these are the launches of space rockets. Burning fuel "burns out" large holes in the ozone layer. It was once assumed that these "holes" were being closed. It turned out not. They have been around for quite some time.

Secondly, planes. Especially flying at altitudes of 12-15 km. The steam and other substances emitted by them destroy ozone. But, at the same time, aircraft flying below 12 km. Give an increase in ozone. In cities, it is one of the components of photochemical smog.

Thirdly, nitrogen oxides. They are thrown out by the same planes, but most of all they are released from the soil surface, especially during the decomposition of nitrogen fertilizers.

Fourth, it is chlorine and its compounds with oxygen. A huge amount (up to 700 thousand tons) of this gas enters the atmosphere, primarily from the decomposition of freons. Freons are gases that do not enter into any chemical reactions near the surface of the Earth, boiling at room temperature, and therefore sharply increase their volume, which makes them good atomizers. Since their temperature decreases as they expand, freons are widely used in the refrigeration industry.

Ozone properties:

- Ability to absorb biologically hazardous ultraviolet radiation from the sun;
- Ozone is the strongest oxidizing agent (simply poison), so ground-level ozone is dangerous;
- Ability to absorb infrared radiation from the earth's surface;
- Ability to directly and indirectly influence the chemical composition of the atmosphere;

There is "good ozone" and "bad ozone". "Bad ozone" is what scientists call phytochemical smog. Ozone in the stratosphere is usually referred to as "good" ozone, as it protects the earth from damaging radiation. Most of the remaining 10 percent of "bad" ozone resides in the surface layer of the atmosphere - the troposphere - and, once it reaches certain concentrations, it poses a risk to the health and well-being of the population.

The most significant stages in the destruction of the ozone layer:

- 1) Emissions: as a result of human activities, as well as in as a result of natural processes on Earth, gases containing halogens (bromine and chlorine) are emitted (released), i.e. substances that deplete the ozone layer.
- 2) Accumulation (emitted gases containing halogens accumulate (accumulate) in the lower atmospheric layers, and under the influence of wind and air flows

move to regions that are not in direct proximity to the sources of such gas emissions).

3) Movement (accumulated gases containing halogens move to the stratosphere with the help of air currents).

4) Transformation (most of the gases containing halogens, under the influence of ultraviolet radiation from the Sun in the stratosphere, are converted into easily reacting halogen gases, as a result of which the destruction of the ozone layer in the polar regions of the globe is relatively more active).

5) Chemical reactions (easily reacting halogen gases cause the destruction of stratospheric ozone; the factor contributing to the reactions is polar stratospheric clouds).

6) Removal (under the influence of air currents, easily reacting halogen gases return to the troposphere, where, due to the moisture and rain present in the clouds, they are separated, and thus completely removed from the atmosphere).

This problem is relevant today and the following measures are necessary to further preserve the ozone layer:

1) Continue monitoring the ozone layer to quickly track unforeseen changes; to ensure the implementation by the countries of the adopted agreements;

2) Continue work to identify the causes of ozone layer changes and evaluate the harmful properties of new chemicals in relation to ozone depletion and the impact on climate change in general.

3) Continue to provide information on technologies and substitute compounds that allow refrigeration, air conditioning and thermal insulation foams to be used without damaging the ozone layer.

On September 16, 1987, the Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer was signed. To commemorate this event, in 1994 the UN General Assembly by a special resolution declared September 16 as the annual International Day for the Protection of the Ozone Layer.¹⁰³

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